

Candy Leaf: Stevia

DOI:

Introduction

Stevia rebaudiana (Bertoni) is an emerging crop and alternative source of non-caloric natural sweetness. It is commonly known as candy leaf, sweet leaf, or sugar leaf. It is a medicinal plant, belongs to Asteraceae family. Stevia leaves have been used since ancient times for various purposes throughout the world. Leaves of Stevia produce diterpene glycosides (Stevioside and Rebaudiosides) which are high potency natural sweetener and substitute to sugar, being 250-300 times sweeter than sucrose.

Stevia plant
(*Stevia rebaudiana*).

Stevia flower
(*Stevia rebaudiana*).

In present time people are very calorie conscious which increases use of Stevia in preparation of non-calorie food stuffs and become a major sweetening agent in food products in south-east Asia. India has suitable conditions for the cultivation of Stevia. It has been found that Indian Stevia sp. Plant gives a higher stevioside yield of 10 to 18 % in comparison to the reported 8 to 12 % from other countries. India itself is also stepping forward to compete in the Stevia sweetener international market.

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History and Use:

Stevia rebaudiana has been used for more than 1500 years by the Guarani people of Brazil and Paraguay, who called it *ka'a he'ê* ("sweet herb"), to sweeten the local yerba mate tea, as medicine, and as a "sweet treat". In 1899, botanist Moises Santiago Bertoni first described the plant as growing in eastern Paraguay, and observed its sweet taste.

In 1931, chemists **M. Bridel and R. Lavielle** are isolated the glycosides stevioside and rebaudioside that give the leaves their sweet taste. The exact structure of the aglycone steviol and its glycoside were published in 1955.

Cultivation

Stevia rebaudiana plants which are found in the wild in semiarid habitats ranging from grassland to mountain terrain, do produce seeds, but only a small percentage of the seeds germinate. Planting cloned stevia is a more effective method of reproduction.

Stevia rebaudiana has been grown on an experimental basis in Ontario, Canada since 1987 to determine the feasibility of commercial cultivation. Duke university researchers developed a strategic plan to assist farmers and exporters in Paraguay to compete in the global market for stevia.

Today, *Stevia rebaudiana* is cultivated and used to sweeten food in Asia including China (since 1984), Korea, Thailand, Philippines, Indonesia and Malaysia. It can also be found in Saint Kitts and Nevis, Brazil, Colombia, Peru, Paraguay, Uruguay and Israel. According to the European Journal of Microbiology and Immunology 5, *Stevia rebaudiana* can be used effectively to kill Lyme disease in vitro

Nutritional and Health benefit

Stevia leaves on dry weight basis have energy value is 2.7 k cal g⁻¹. Stevioside, the major sweetener presents in leaf and stem tissues of Stevia. Diterpene glycosides are many times sweetener than sucrose and can be utilized as a natural alternative sweetening agents that are now available to the diet conscious consumers. The potential uses of Stevia which produces stevioside, a non-caloric sweetener that does not metabolize in the human body, hence control blood sugar level. This is more important, especially in the context of the current social movement towards more natural foods. Increased incidence of diabetes in India and abroad and growing concern over the safety of some chemical sweeteners, there is a need for a natural non-caloric sweetener with acceptable taste and health properties. Stevia is a well-known non-caloric sweetening properties and a therapeutic agent serve as an efficient medication for diabetes, hypertension, myocardial and anti-microbial infections, dental troubles and tumors.

The natural sweeteners of Stevia leaves, called steviol glycosides, are diterpenes, isolated and identified as stevioside, steviolbioside, rebaudioside A, B, C, D, E, F and dulcoside. Stevioside was reported to be the most abundant Stevia glycoside (4-13 % w/w) found in the plant leaves. It is followed by rebaudioside-A (2-4 % w/w), rebaudioside-C (1-2 % w/w) and dulcoside-A (0.4-0.7 % w/w). Steviolbioside, rebaudioside B, D, E and F were also identified in the leaf extracts, but as minor constituents. The glycosides found mainly in the leaves of the

plant, make up to 15 % of the content, depending on variety. Its amount depends on growing conditions as well as on the adoption of modern agronomical techniques.

Conclusion

Stevia is an emerging crop which produce non-caloric herbal sweetener. Stevioside, the major sweetener presents in leaf and stem tissues of Stevia. It is an alternate substitute of sugar. Stevia is high potential natural sweetening agent that highly nutritious, delicious and non-toxic. It is also used in food additives for enhancing the flavours without affecting the blood sugar level with great therapeutic values.

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